

**KA210-SCH - Small-scale partnerships in
school education (KA210-SCH), E+ Project: “*SteM rAising
EnviRonmenTal Scientists*”
meeting in Cordoba, Spain**

Dates: 06th-09th May 2025

Meeting venue: Seneca School (pre-primary building)

Escritor Almeida Garret Street, 1 - 14014, Cordoba

AGENDA

Day 1 (Tuesday 06h May 2025)

9:30- 10:15h	Welcome and opening of the meeting	Séneca School Headmaster + Erasmus Coordinators
10:15-10:30h	Performance by a Séneca School Students	Séneca School
10:30-11:00h	Coffe break	-
11:00-11:45h	School presentation by students and Tour	Seneca School students
11:45- 12:15h	Short presentations of Partners organizations (5'- 10' each partner)	Project Coordinators of each School

12:15-13:00h	Presentation of the planning of the meeting (objectives, timeline)	Séneca school and all partners
13:00-14:00h	Lunch Break (at the school's canteen)	All partners
16:00-18:00	Analysis of the sustainable acclimatization elements of the patios of Córdoba	All partners

Day 2 (Wednesday 07th may 2025)

09:30-09:45	Activation activities	Séneca School
09:45-10:15	Logo Contest presentation	Dumlupinar İlkokulu (Türkiye)school
10:15-10:30	Debate and collective reflection	All partners
10:30-11:00	Coffee Break	All partners
11:00-12:00	Scientifics Journal Presentation	Szkola Podstawowa z Oddziałami Dwujęzycznymi nr 20 im. Jana Gutenberga Fundacji Szkolnej w Warszawie (Poland)
12:00-12:15	Debate and collective reflection	All partners
13:00-14:00h	Lunch Break (at the school's canteen)	All partners
16:00-18:00	Visit Analysis of the use of water from the Guadalquivir River in the Mosque of Córdoba	All partners

Day 3 (Thursday 08th May 2025)

09:30-11:45	Cultural visit "Medina Azahara"	All partners
11:45-12:15	Travel to la Breña II reservoir, Almodovar del Río (Córdoba)	All partners
12:15-13:30	Solar-powered boat trip with lunch on La Breña II reservoir, Almodóvar del Río (Córdoba)	All partners

Day 4 (Friday 09th May 2025)

09:30-09:45	Activation activities	Séneca School
09:45-10:30	Scratch,s Taller "ecologic way to program"	Séneca School
10:30-11:00	Coffee Break	All partners
11:00-11:30	Installing intelligent trash bins in school during a technical excursion presentation	Szkola Podstawowa z Oddziałami Dwujęzycznymi nr 20 im. Jana Gutenberga Fundacji Szkolnej w Warszawie (Poland)
11:30-12:00	Certificates ceremony - End of the meeting	All partners